

INTERNAL QUANTUM EFFICIENCY AND CURRENT-VOLTAGE CHARACTERISTICS MODELING OF ZNO/CZTS BASED THIN FILM SOLAR CELLS

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Abstract:

CZTS is the most promising solar cell till date in terms of high efficiency, low-cost, non-radioactive and environmental friendly behavior. Based on the concept of the Perturbation Theory, an analytical approach has been developed to deduce the internal quantum efficiency and current-voltage characteristics of ZnO/CZTS based thin-film solar cell having lightly doped absorber layer. An analytical approach is used rather than numerical method to reduce time and also to study the physics of the device more.

Key words: Internal quantum efficiency, J-V characteristics, heterojunction cell, CZTS Thin Film Solar Cell, Perturbation Theory

I. INTRODUCTION

Katagiri et al. [1] was the first to work on fabrication of CZTS (Cu₂ZnSnS₄) based thin film solar cell with 6.7% efficiency using the preferential etching technique which shows that it is a promising solar cell till date. CZTS stands for copper Zinc Tin Selenide which is a quaternary semiconductor where each of the elements is structurally related compounds. The abundance of the elements used in CZTS makes it an inexpensive material. It is an emerging absorber material for solar cell due to its direct band semiconductor properties having a band gap of 1.4-1.5eV and high optical absorption coefficient of 10⁴ cm⁻¹[2]. Furthermore, this device has a super-substrate device structure of ZnO in emitter side that helps in the absorption of the photons due to its transparency and high absorption quality [3].

Till date it was known that CIGS based thin film solar cell is a best option, but the use of cadmium sulphide makes it radioactive and environmentally hazardous. But in CZTS based thin film solar cell ZnO (zinc oxide) is used which has no hazardous effect on the environment. Moreover, the elements indium and gallium is rare in earth-crust which is introduced in the manufacturing of the CIGS based thin film solar cell thus making it more expensive material which is now

replaced with zinc and tin in CZTS based thin film solar cell.

In the literature, till to date, a few studies have been made regarding the substitution of CIGS with CZTS [1-8]. Fabrication based study that altered the thin film solar cell structurally was made by Puvaneswaran et al. [4]. No analytic and modeling approach was introduced to understand its physics. Anjan et al. [8] developed an analytical expression for the external voltage dependent photocurrent by assuming a uniform electric field in the absorber layer and many other parameters. When modeling approach was introduced, it had many fitting parameters to it, where issues like high-doping, low-doping, uniform electric field across the depletion region, loss of photons during the incidence, etc. were ignored.

In this work an attempt has been made to develop an analytical model for the internal quantum efficiency and current-voltage characteristics including the effects of the series resistance and the variation of load voltage on the photocurrent by applying the concept of the perturbation theory. Till to date, this is the first analytical model for the CZTS based thin film solar cell.

II. ANALYSIS

The expression for net current density of a solar cell is

$$J(V) = J_d(V) - J_{ph}(V) \quad (1)$$

where $J_d(V)$ is the dark saturation current density and $J_{ph}(V)$ is the photo-generated current density. Since ZnO absorbs high energetic photons with very short diffusion length and very thin width, the photo-generated current component in the emitter region is

negligible. Hence, J_{ph} can be approximated as the photo-generated current component in the depletion region only. As the base (CZTS) region is lightly doped, all the absorber layer is depleted and the electric field in the depletion region can be reasonably assumed as constant. This voltage dependent field can be expressed as

$$E(V) = \frac{V_{bi} - (V - JR_s)}{W_b} \quad (2)$$

where W_b is the width of the depletion region in the CIGS layer. In Ref. [9, 10], W_b is calculated assuming the p-n junction as homojunction, a fitting parameter V_0 is used instead of V_{bi} and the voltage drop across the intrinsic layer JR_s is calculated from a measured value of R_s .

Using Equation (2) and following the derivation in Ref.[11,12], the total photo-generated current J_{ph} for all wavelengths present in the sun spectrum can be calculated.

A. Derivation of Photo-generated Current Density

The photogeneration current in depletion region is the sum of the photogenerated electron current (J_n) and hole current(J_p). Since electric field is the dominant mechanism for current conduction in the depletion region, diffusion component of these currents are negligible. The basic equations required to deduce these drift-dominated currents are:

$$J_n = qn\mu_n E \quad (3)$$

$$J_p = qp\mu_p E \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dJ_n}{dx} = \frac{qn}{\tau_n} - qG \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dJ_p}{dx} = -\frac{qp}{\tau_p} + qG \quad (6)$$

where μ_n (μ_p) is the electron (hole) mobility, τ_n τ_p is the electron (hole) lifetime. G is the wavelength-dependent optical generation rate given by:

$$G = \alpha(\lambda) \frac{I(\lambda)\lambda}{hc} e^{-\alpha_1(\lambda)W_E} e^{-\alpha(\lambda)x} = \alpha(\lambda)G_0 e^{-\alpha(\lambda)x} \quad (7)$$

Combining the above equations [Equations (3) and (5) and Equations (4) and (6)] results in first order differential equations of electrons and holes as

$$\frac{dn}{dx} + \left[-\frac{1}{\mu_n \tau_n E} + \frac{d}{dx} \ln E \right] n = -G_n \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{dp}{dx} + \left[\frac{1}{\mu_p \tau_p E} + \frac{d}{dx} \ln E \right] p = G_p \quad (9)$$

$$\text{where } M_n = \frac{1}{\mu_n \tau_n E}, \quad G_n = \frac{G}{\mu_n E} \quad \text{and} \quad M_p = \frac{1}{\mu_p \tau_p E},$$

$$G_p = \frac{G}{\mu_p E}.$$

Since the hole and electron start drifting immediately after generation i.e. $p(W_E) \approx 0$ and $n(W_E + x_p) \approx 0$, the solutions of the electron and holes are obtained as

$$n(x) = \frac{\alpha G_0 e^{-\alpha W_E}}{(M_n + \alpha) \mu_n E_{n0}} (e^{-\alpha x} - e^{M_n(x-x_p) - \alpha x_p}) \quad (10)$$

$$p(x) = \frac{\alpha G_0 e^{-\alpha W_E}}{(M_p - \alpha) \mu_p E_p} (e^{-\alpha x} - e^{-M_p x}) \quad (11)$$

The photocurrent density for holes and electron drifting correspondingly towards the bottom and top contact can be expressed as the spatial average over the depletion region and can be expressed as

$$J_n(V, \lambda) = \frac{\alpha q G_0 e^{-\alpha W_E}}{(M_n + \alpha)} (J_0 + J_{n1}) \quad (12)$$

$$J_p(V, \lambda) = \frac{\alpha q G_0 e^{-\alpha W_E}}{(M_p - \alpha) \mu_p E} (J_0 + J_{p1}) \quad (13)$$

where,

$$J_0 = \frac{1}{\alpha} e^{-\alpha W_E} (1 - e^{-\alpha x_p})$$

$$J_{n1} = \frac{1}{M_n} e^{M_n(W_E - x_p) - \alpha x_p} (1 - e^{M_n x_p})$$

$$J_{p1} = \frac{1}{M_p} e^{-M_p W_E} (e^{-M_p x_p} - 1)$$

The internal quantum efficiency at any given wavelength then can be determined from the following expression

$$\eta(\lambda) = \frac{J_{ph0}(\lambda)}{qG_0(\lambda)} \times 100\% \quad (14)$$

The total photogenerated current J_{ph0} at a particular wavelength λ then can be expressed as

$$J_{ph0}(V, \lambda) = J_n(V, \lambda) + J_p(V, \lambda) \quad (15)$$

The total photogenerated current density is found by integrating over all incident photon wavelengths of the solar spectra, i.e.,

$$J_{ph}(V) = \int_0^\infty J_{ph0}(V, \lambda) d\lambda \quad (16)$$

B. Derivation of Dark Current Density

Since the recombination current dominates over the diffusion current, the dark current density J_d can be approximated as the forward biased recombination

current density in the depletion region and can be expressed as [7]

$$J_d(V) = J_0 \left(e^{\frac{q(V - IR_s)}{nKT}} - 1 \right) \quad (17)$$

$$J_0 = \frac{qn_i x_p}{2\sqrt{\tau_n \tau_p}}$$

where n is the diode ideality factor and In Ref. [7], n is used as a fitting parameter. In this work, the actual value of $n = 2$ is used. Therefore, this work does not need to use any fitting parameters.

C. Analytical Derivation of Total Current Density

Combining Eqns. (16) and (17) with Eqn. (1) results in

$$J_L(V) = -J_{ph}(V) + J_0 \left[e^{\frac{V - J_L(V)R_s}{nKT}} - 1 \right] \quad (18)$$

From equation (17) we can see that $J_L(V)$ is not possible to be found due to its present on the right hand side. To resolve the problem, all the previous literatures used numerical methods. But in our work we approached the problem analytically by using the Perturbation Theory.

Under short circuit condition $J_L(V=0) \approx -J_{ph}(V)$ where $R_s \rightarrow 0$. We can use this value of $J_L(V=0)$ on the right hand side of equation (18) and hence determine $J_L(\delta V)$ provided that $\delta V \rightarrow 0$. In this way the values of the load current, $J_L(V)$ can be found for any range of values of V .

III. RESULT

In this section the results obtained from the analytical procedure outlined in the previous section are presented and analyzed. The using the air mass (AM) 1.5 global spectrum from the ASTM G-173-03 standard[11] as, the J-V characteristics of ZnO/CZTS thin film solar cells is plotted and analyzed in this work. The absorption coefficients for ZnO and CZTS are obtained from the absorption curves in Ref. [12].

When the absorber width increases the carriers have to travel a longer distance to reach the contact. As a results, the carriers have to suffer a greater recombination losses i.e. the more carriers are lost and hence, both the open circuit voltage and the short circuit current decrease. The Fig 1(a) shows these trends. A closer look of Fig. 1(a) also shows that the open circuit voltage decreases at a slower pace than the short circuit current. This is because open circuit voltage changes logarithmically, whereas short circuit current does not. Fig 1(b) shows the effect of absorber width variation on the internal quantum efficiency. Surprisingly, this figure shows that internal quantum efficiency (η) is

independent of thebase width. This is because η is calculated under short circuit condition ($J = 0$). As aresult, any change in current density due to the change in W_b is notreflected in the electric field therefore electric field(E), photo generation current(J_{ph}) and the internal quantum efficiency remains constant.

(a)

(b)

Fig 1(a) Effect of the Absorber Width (W_b) on the J-V Characteristics of ZnO/CZTS based solar cell. (b) Effect of the Absorber Width (W_b) on Internal quantum efficiency of ZnO/CZTS based solar cell.

Fig 2 shows the effect of different intensities on the J-V characteristic. As expected, this curve shows that increase in the intensity results in improvement in the J-V characteristics. Again, due to logarithmic change the open circuit voltage changes is slower than the short circuit current change.

Fig2 Effect of the Intensity Variation on the J-V Characteristics of ZnO/CZTS based solar cell (R=0.15,n=1.5,Rs=0.2).

In Fig 3(a) we can see the effect on the J-V characteristic when the electron's lifetime-mobility product is changed. It is observed that when the electron's lifetime-mobility product increases both the open circuit voltage and the short circuit current increase, but the change in short circuit current is not significant. This less effect of short circuit current density is also reflected in Fig 3(b), where it has been observed that the change in internal quantum efficiency against the change in electron lifetime is slightly significant for longer wavelengths only. This can be explained as follows. Photo-generated electrons for short wavelengths are created near the emitter, whereas those for longer wavelengths are created near the base side. Since electrons move from the base towards the emitter due to the built-in field in a n+p junction, electrons of longer wavelengths have to cover longer distance and hence, suffer higher recombination loss. As a result, internal quantum efficiency for longer wavelength decreases as electron lifetime decreases.

(a)

(b)

Fig 3 (a)Effect of the Electron transport on the J-V Characteristics of ZnO/CZTS based solar cell (R=0.15, n=1.5, Rs=0.2) (b) Effect of the Electron transport on the Internal quantum efficiency of ZnO/CZTS based solar cell.

In Fig 4(a) the hole's lifetime-mobility product is varied and its effect on the J-V characteristic is observed. It is observed that when product of hole-lifetime and mobility increases both the open circuit voltage and the short circuit current increase, but change in the short circuit current density is now comparable with the change in open circuit voltage. This effect can be explained with the help of Fig 4(b), where it has been observed that internal quantum efficiency is less for short wavelengths compared to that for the longer wavelengths. Like electrons, photogenerated holes for short wavelengths are created near the emitter side, whereas, those for longer wavelengths are created near the base side; but, due to the built-in electric field, hole for short wavelengths has to travel a longer distance than those for longer wavelengths. Therefore, for short wavelengths, internal quantum efficiency decreases. Both the effects observed in figure 3 and 4 are as expected because when the lifetime of the holes and electrons increase, the level of recombination decreases resulting in less carrier loss. Hence we get more open circuit voltage and short circuit current for the J-V characteristics. From both the graphs it is also evident that hole transport has a greater effect than that of electron transport. This happens because when the holes and

Fig 4 (a) Effect of the Hole transport on the J-V Characteristics of ZnO/CZTS based solar cell ($R=0.15$, $n=1.5$, $R_s=0.2$). (b) Effect of the Hole transport on the Internal quantum efficiency of ZnO/CZTS based solar cell.

electrons are formed in the depletion region, the hole has to travel a greater distance than the electrons to complete the contact. As a result it has a higher effect than the electrons. Overall the internal quantum efficiency of the system is effected more by the change in the hole lifetime than the change in the electron lifetime.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work an analytical model has been developed for internal quantum efficiency and current-voltage characteristic of CZTS based thin film solar cell for the first time in the literature. This model includes the effect of R_s and variation of V_L . From the results it has been observed that on decreasing the width of the base and increasing the intensity there is an improvement in both internal quantum efficiency (η) and current-voltage (J-V) characteristics. On the other hand, both η and J-V characteristics are sensitive to hole transport. It is also observed that internal quantum efficiency for hole transport is higher for longer wavelengths than that of

shorter wavelengths. Therefore, the proposed model in this work explains elaborately about the physical insight of CZTS based thin film solar cell. Moreover, being an analytical model its computational efficiency is high.

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